

Reactions of 2, 3, 4-Trichlorothiophene with Magnesium

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2, 3, 4-Trichlorothiophene reacts with magnesium in the presence of ethylene bromide as an entrainer to give 3, 4-dichlorothiophene and (trichloro-2-thienyl)-magnesium halide. A probable mechanism has been discussed.

IN connection with studies concerning the synthesis of thermally stable compounds we needed (3,4-dichloro-2-thienyl)-magnesium reagent. The obvious route to such a reagent seemed, by analogy with the preparation of (trichloro-2-thienyl)magnesium halide¹, to be the reaction of 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene with magnesium. In this paper we wish to describe such a reaction under various conditions.

Results and Discussion

2,3,4-Trichlorothiophene (I) (x moles) reacts in THF with magnesium ($2x$ g-atoms) in the presence of ethylene bromide (x moles) as an entrainer to give, subsequent to carbonation, trichloro-2-thiophenecarboxylic acid (II) (45%) and 3,4-dichlorothiophene (III) (36%). Instead of carbonation, if chlorotrimethylsilane is added to the reaction mixture, (trichloro-2-thienyl)trimethylsilane (IV) and (III) are formed almost in equimolar amounts. The formation of trichloro-2-thiophenecarboxylic acid (II) by carbonation and (trichloro-2-thienyl)trimethylsilane (IV) by reaction with chlorotrimethylsilane indicate the presence of (trichloro-2-thienyl)magnesium halide (V) in the reaction mixture.

Although there is no definite evidence of how these products are derived, it has been proposed that ethylene bromide reacts with magnesium to give β -bromoethylmagnesium bromide which rapidly eliminates a molecule of magnesium bromide to produce ethylene². It was thought that 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene (I) might behave as an efficient trapping agent for β -bromoethylmagnesium bromide and could have been metalated by it to give the Grignard reagent (V) and ethyl bromide. But this possibility was discounted because no ethyl bromide was formed during the reaction. Another explanation was considered in this connection. Stable telomers of the type $\text{BrMg}(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{MgBr}$, if formed as a result of the reaction between ethylene bromide and magnesium, might metalate (I) to give (V). Since the products of the reaction between ethylene bromide and magnesium do not give Color Test I³ and also do not react at all with (I) even in the presence of magnesium under similar conditions, such an explanation for the formation of (V) seems unlikely. In any case neither mechanism can reasonably account for the formation of (III) in yields as high as 36-42%.

The formation of 3,4-dichlorothiophene (III) and (trichloro-2-thienyl)magnesium halide (V), however,

It is known²⁻⁵ that ethylene bromide reacts with magnesium to form ethylene and magnesium bromide.

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can be explained satisfactorily if it is assumed that the first step of the reaction is the formation of (3,4-dichloro-2-thienyl)magnesium halide (VI). This Grignard reagent then metalates the unreacted 2,3,4-

trichlorothiophene (I) to produce 3,4-dichlorothiophene (III) and (trichloro-2-thienyl)magnesium halide (V).

In support of the existence of (VI) as an intermediate we have observed the following. Before sufficient time was allowed for the reaction (I) to be complete, if chlorotrimethylsilane was added, both (trichloro-2-thienyl)trimethylsilane (IV) and (3,4-dichloro-2-thienyl)trimethylsilane (VII) were formed in addition to (III). Table I shows the product ratio of (IV) to (VII) at different times. It may be seen from the Table that the yield of (VII) and hence of (VI) drops gradually to practically nothing as the reaction goes to near completion. This is consistent with the proposed mechanism. Table I also shows how the ratio of (I) to (III) changes with time to almost unity.

TABLE I—PRODUCT RATIOS OF DERIVATIVES OF THE GRIGNARD REAGENTS FORMED DURING THE REACTION OF 2, 3, 4-TRICHLOROTHIOPHENE WITH MAGNESIUM ($C_2H_4Br_2$ ENTRAINER)

Time* hr	Silylated product ratio, IV/VII**	Hydrolysed product ratio, I/III†
0.5 =	8	1.40
1.0 @	14	1.27
3.0 ≠	35	1.20
30.0	300	1.05

*After the initiation of the reaction (see experimental).

**IV and VII are respectively, (trichloro-2-thienyl)trimethylsilane and (3, 4-dichloro-2-thienyl)trimethylsilane¹⁹, estimated by glc (area ratio).

† I and III are respectively, 2, 3, 4-trichlorothiophene and 3, 4-dichlorothiophene; estimated by glc (area ratio).

= Approximately one-quarter of the entrainer has been added, the entrainer and 2, 3, 4-trichlorothiophene being used in equimolar amounts.

@ Approximately one-half of the entrainer has been added.

≠ One hour after the addition of the total amount of the entrainer.

It appears⁷ that similar metalation reactions during the preparation of 2-thienylmagnesium halides from 2-halothiophenes and magnesium do not occur. This indicates that the 5-hydrogen of (I), which contains three electron-withdrawing chlorine atoms, is more acidic than the 5-hydrogen atoms of 2-halothiophenes.

When 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene is treated with three equivalents of magnesium and two equivalents of ethylene bromide, the yields of (II) and (III), subsequent to carbonation, were 42 and 43%, respectively. No evidence for the formation of a di-Grignard reagent was obtained in this experiment. 2,3,4-Trichlorothiophene does not react to any significant extent with either magnesium or copper-magnesium alloy (39% copper) either in the presence of a catalyst such as ethylene bromide or without it.

2,3,4-Trichlorothiophene undergoes easy metalation and metal-halogen exchange reactions with alkylolithium or -magnesium halide reagents. The details of this study will be published soon.

Experimental

The reactions were carried out under a positive pressure of dry, oxygen-free nitrogen. The ethereal solvents were dried over sodium-wire and distilled prior to use from sodium-benzophenone ketyl. Magnesium turnings were from the Mallinckrodt Chemical Works. Tetrachlorothiophene was obtained commercially and used without further purification. *n*-Butyllithium in hexane was from Foote Mineral Co. and was used at the strength determined by the supplier. Ir spectra were determined as nujol mulls using a Perkin Elmer Model 21 spectrometer. Nmr spectra were recorded in carbon tetrachloride, using a Varian A60 spectrometer. Glc analyses were carried out on an F and M Model 500 Gas Chromatograph using a $4' \times \frac{1}{8}''$ column packed with 15% Silicone Gum Rubber on Chromosorb W (60–80 mesh). The yields were based on the starting 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene. The temperatures quoted are uncorrected.

Preparation of 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene

(i) *From trichloro-2-thienyllithium⁸ or -magnesium halide¹ reagent*: To a solution of trichloro-2-thienyllithium⁸, prepared from tetrachlorothiophene (11.1 g, 0.05 mole) and *n*-butyllithium (0.05 mole) in ether (100 ml) at -15° was added 3*N* HCl (100 ml) slowly. The reaction mixture was stirred for one-half hour and worked up in the usual way to give 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene (7.1 g, 76%), b.p. $76.5^\circ/10$ mm, n_D^{20} 1.5862 (cited⁹: b.p. 209.6° , n_D^{20} 1.5861).

When trichloro-2-thienylmagnesium halide¹, prepared from tetrachlorothiophene (11.1 g, 0.05 mole), magnesium (2.4 g, 0.1 g-atom) and ethylene bromide (9.4 g, 0.05 mole) as an entrainer in THF (160 ml), was hydrolyzed in the above manner, the yield of 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene of similar purity was 6.2 g (66%). In a second preparation the yield was 70%.

(ii) *From tetrachlorothiophene and lithium aluminium hydride*: Tetrachlorothiophene (11.1 g, 0.05 mole) and lithium aluminium hydride (1.4 g, 0.05 mole) were stirred together in ether (110 ml) at room temperature for 3 days. During this period the yield of 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene as determined by glc of a hydrolysed aliquot was 25%. The mixture was refluxed in ether for two days when the yield rose to 35% and then remained constant. Ether was distilled off and the mixture was heated between

80°–85° for three more days. After hydrolysis and workup as above there was obtained 3.2 g (34%) of 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene.

Reaction of 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene with magnesium

(i) *In the presence of ethylene bromide (as entrainer^{1,2}):* To 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene (4.7 g, 0.025 mole) free from tetrachlorothiophene, and magnesium (1.2 g, 0.05 g-atom) in THF (10 ml) was added a few ml of a solution prepared from ethylene bromide (4.7 g, 0.025 mole) in THF (80 ml). An exothermic reaction started. Color Test I⁶ was positive within three minutes. The remaining ethylene bromide solution was added dropwise over a period of two hours while moderating the reaction by water bath. After stirring for 30 hr at room temperature an aliquot was withdrawn and reacted with excess chlorotrimethylsilane and the products examined by glc. 3,4-Dichlorothiophene and trichloro-2-thienyltrimethylsilane were formed in 44% and 46% yield, respectively. The reaction mixture was then carbonated by passing gaseous carbon dioxide for 5 hr (although the Color Test I⁶ was negative within one-half hour). Usual work-up gave (a) 3,4-dichlorothiophene (1.5 g, 36%), b.p. 94°/38 mm, n_D^{20} 1.5755 (cited⁹: 182.01°, n_D^{20} 1.5762), identical (glc, ir and nmr) with a sample prepared from the acid hydrolysis of 3,4-dichloro-2,5-dithiothiophene¹⁰; and (b) trichloro-2-thiophenecarboxylic acid (2.6 g, 45%), m.p. 225°–226° (cited¹¹: 224°), identical (mixed m.p. and ir) with a sample prepared by the carbonation of trichloro-2-thienyl-magnesium halide¹. No ethyl bromide was formed not even in a glc detectable amount. The above experiment was repeated four times with similar results.

In a separate run the course of the reaction was followed in the following manner. At a definite time two small aliquots were withdrawn, one was hydrolyzed and the other treated with chlorotrimethylsilane (excess). The products of each aliquot were extracted in ether and analysed by glc. Table I shows the ratios of the yields of (trichloro-2-thienyl)trimethylsilane¹ and (3,4-dichloro-2-thienyl)trimethylsilane (VII), at various times. (VII) was made for comparison from 3,4-dichloro-2-thienyllithium and ClSiMe₃.¹²

When three equivalents of magnesium and two equivalents of ethylene bromide were used 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene reacts in THF to give, subsequent to carbonation, 3,4-dichlorothiophene (1.9 g, 42%) and trichloro-2-thiophenecarboxylic acid (2.5 g, 43%), m.p. 225°–226° (mixed m.p. undepressed).

(ii) *In the presence of a catalytic amount of ethylene bromide:* To 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene (2.35 g, 0.0125 mole) and magnesium (0.3 g, 0.0125 g-atom) in THF (50 ml) was added a few drops (0.001 mole, 3%) of ethylene bromide and the mixture was stirred vigorously at room temperature. The color of the reaction mixture changed to brownish grey. Within five minutes Color Test I⁶ was positive. After stirring for six hours an aliquot was withdrawn, treated with excess chlorotrimethylsilane and the products examined by glc. The yields of various products were approximately as follows: (trichloro-2-thienyl)trimethylsilane, 4–5%; 2,3,4-trichlorothio-

phene, 88–90%; 3,4-dichlorothiophene, 3–4%. No peak in the glc corresponding to (3,4-dichloro-2-thienyl)trimethylsilane or 2,5-bis(trimethylsilyl)-3,4-dichlorothiophene was detected.

In the above reaction when magnesium was replaced by copper-magnesium alloy¹³ (39% copper), the yields of the various products were essentially the same. 2,3,4-Trichlorothiophene did not react with magnesium in the absence of a catalyst such as ethylene bromide.

(iii) *In the presence of anhydrous magnesium bromide:* Magnesium bromide was prepared³ by the reaction of ethylene bromide (1.88 g, 0.01 mole) with Grignard grade magnesium (0.5 g, 0.022 g-atom) in THF (35 ml) at 0° to 5° for 3 hr. Color Test I⁶ was negative and the reaction mixture did not contain any ethylene bromide (glc). 2,3,4-Trichlorothiophene (2.35 g, 12.5 mmoles) was then added and the mixture stirred for 32 hr at room temperature. Color Test I⁶ was negative even at the end of this period, and no perceptible colour change was noticed although the surface of the magnesium metal appeared clean. Glc of a hydrolyzed aliquot showed the absence of 3, 4-dichlorothiophene. Similarly no silylated products *viz.*, (trichloro-2-thienyl) trimethylsilane, (3, 4-dichloro-2-thienyl) trimethylsilane or 2,5-bis(trimethylsilyl)-3,4-dichlorothiophene, were formed when an aliquot was treated with chlorotrimethylsilane.

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